

EMBL Services for Structural Biology

EMBL Hamburg
EMBL Grenoble
EMBL Heidelberg

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Ilkovičova 8, Bratislava

Structural Biology and Imaging Services

4D

Molecules to Ecosystems
 - life in context -

Structural Biology and Imaging Services
 - scale bridging

Experimental Methods for Structural Biology

AlphaFold

AlphaFold
Protein Structure Database
Developed by DeepMind and EMBL-EBI

Article

Highly accurate protein structure prediction for the human proteome

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Open access

Check for updates

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Protein structures can provide invaluable information, both for reasoning about biological processes and for enabling interventions such as structure-based drug development or targeted mutagenesis. After decades of effort, 17% of the total residues in human protein sequences are covered by an experimentally determined structure¹. Here we markedly expand the structural coverage of the proteome by applying the state-of-the-art machine learning method, AlphaFold², at a scale that covers almost the entire human proteome (98.5% of human proteins). The resulting dataset covers 58% of residues with a confident prediction, of which a subset (36% of all residues) have very high confidence. We introduce several metrics developed by building on the AlphaFold model and use them to interpret the dataset, identifying strong multi-domain predictions as well as regions that are likely to be disordered. Finally, we provide some case studies to illustrate how high-quality predictions could be used to generate biological hypotheses. We are making our predictions freely available to the community and anticipate that routine large-scale and high-accuracy structure prediction will become an important tool that will allow new questions to be addressed from a structural perspective.

The monumental success of the human genome project revealed new worlds of protein-coding genes, and many researchers set out to map these proteins to their structures^{3,4}. Thanks to the efforts of individual laboratories and dedicated structural genomics initiatives, more than 50,000 human protein structures have now been deposited, making *Homo sapiens* by far the best represented species in the Protein Data Bank (PDB)⁵. Despite this intensive study, only 35% of human proteins map to a PDB entry, and in many cases the structure covers only a fragment of the sequence⁶. Experimental structure determination requires overcoming many time-consuming hurdles: the protein must be produced in sufficient quantities and purified, appropriate sample preparation conditions chosen and high-quality datasets collected. A target may prove intractable at any stage, and depending on the chosen method, properties such as protein size, the presence of transmembrane regions, presence of disorder or susceptibility to conformational change can be a hindrance^{7,8}. As such, full structural coverage of the proteome remains an outstanding challenge.

Protein structure prediction contributes to closing this gap by providing actionable structural hypotheses quickly and at scale. Previous large-scale structure prediction studies have addressed protein families^{9–12}, specific functional classes^{13,14}, domains identified within whole proteomes⁵ and, in some cases, full chains or complexes^{15,17}. In

particular, projects such as the SWISS-MODEL Repository, Genome3D and ModBase have made valuable contributions by providing access to large numbers of structures and encouraging their free use by the community^{18–21}. Related protein bioinformatics fields have developed alongside structure prediction, including protein design^{22–24}, function annotation^{25–28}, disorder prediction²⁹, and domain identification and classification^{30–32}. Although some of our analyses are inspired by these previous studies, here we focus mainly on structural investigations for which scale and accuracy are particularly beneficial.

Structure prediction has seen substantial progress in recent years, as evidenced by the results of the biennial Critical Assessment of protein Structure Prediction (CASP)^{33–36}. In particular, the latest version of AlphaFold was entered in CASP4 under the team name 'AlphaFold2'. This system used a completely different model from our CASP3 entry³⁷ and demonstrated a considerable improvement over previous methods in terms of providing routinely high accuracy^{38,39}. Backbone predictions with sub-Ångström root mean square deviation (Ca. r.m.s.d.) are now common, and side chains are increasingly accurate⁴⁰. Good results can often be achieved even for challenging proteins without a template structure in the PDB, or with relatively few related sequences to build a multiple sequence alignment (MSA)⁴¹. These improvements are important, because more accurate models permit a wider range of

EMBL Hamburg

MX / SAXS / Biophysics

EMBL

Integrated Facility for Structural Biology and X-ray Imaging

Services at EMBL Hamburg

- EMBL Hamburg operates the entire beamlines beginning at the 'frontend'
- High-throughput Crystallization laboratories equipped with real-time drop imaging and automated crystal harvesting

EMBL SPC Services enabling structural biology research

High-throughput Crystallisation

Molecular Biophysics

Data analysis platform

- **Expertise in Sample preparation & Biophysics**
Consulting, Training, Data analysis, Remote access
- We offer access to **>20 technologies + EMBL beamlines** and SPA Cryo-EM (CSSB) + Data analysis platform.

High-throughput Crystallization Facility

Screens Robots Plates Imaging

CRIMS

- Initial screening 16
- Optimization 13
- LCP
- Additive
- Customized screens
- 2 TTP mosquito
- Scorpion
- CrystalDirect
- Swissci
- Intelli
- LCP
- Hanging drop
- Microbatch
- Formulatrix
- 19 °C and 4 °C

Molecular Biophysics Platform

eSPC Online Data Analysis Platform for molecular biophysics

spc.embl-hamburg.de

FoldAffinity

- 1. Load input
- 2. Fit fluorescence
- 3. Fit unfolded fraction
- 4. Export results
- Tm fitting
- Simulate data
- User guide
- Tutorial
- About

Overview

The binding affinity calculation can be divided into three main steps. First, we load the data, set the ligand concentration of each capillary/well, and the temperature range of interest. Second, we fit each melting curve to obtain the unfolded fraction versus temperature for each ligand concentration. Third, we compute the binding affinity at any fixed temperature from the unfolded fraction versus ligand concentration curve. You can watch FoldAffinity in action in the following video

FoldAffinity

Step 1. Load data
Step 2. Fit the fluorescence curves
Step 3. Fit the unfolded fraction

Fluorescence, DSF, MST, K_{ds}

NEW

Mass Photometry

PhotoMol
Estimating molecular masses in a sample.

Dynamic Light Scattering

Raynals
Estimating sample homogeneity and hydrodynamic radius.

Research in Germany
Land of Ideas

Research in Germany
@ResearchGermany

A New free online tool released by @embl Hamburg enables scientists around the world to easily analyse their data without the need to travel to the laboratory where the data was generated ow.ly/tluP50Gyc8J #OpenScience #MolecularInteractions

Kotov *et al.*, Sci. Rep. 2019
Kotov *et al.*, Prot. Sci. 2020
Burastero *et al.* Acta Crystallogr D. 2021
Niebling *et al.* Sci. Rep. 2021

- **User-friendly**
- **Free** for academic users
- **Quality control** of data
- **Open** access / open code
- **Multiple techniques** & instruments
- **Virtual** teaching
- Export **publication quality figures**

First integrated online data analysis server for molecular biophysics

Scientific service

Research

Our users

Usage

Online, user-friendly and interactive analysis of biophysical data

eSPC novel methods are published

Niebling *et al.* (2021, 2022)
Burastero *et al.* (2021, 2023)

Useful for scientists from the EMBL member states and all around the world

Between 200 and 400 visits¹ per month in 2023

spc.embl-hamburg.de

New SPC services: Going 4D

- Production of active enzymes, **enzymology** studies
- Sample preparation for time-resolved crystallography, production of **microcrystals**

Going 5D

Serial X-ray crystallography @ TREXX P14

Molecular movie on tryptophan synthase catalysis by Serial X-ray Crystallography. Sihyun Sung (Wilmanns group)

12

X-ray imaging at P14: Phase contrast holo tomography

High-Throughput Tomography:

- is fast
- produces a lot of data
- is real isotropic 3D
- is feasible in liquid and with embedded samples
- can be used in correlation with EM and light microscopy

Data Science

X-ray scattering

Streaming data
collection and
structure
determination

MX & SAXS

Integrative modelling

Jan Kosinski group

Nature protocols 2022

Molecular Biophysics

eSPC

First integrated online
data analysis server for
molecular biophysics

X-ray imaging

Liz Duke team

Kidney cylinder with
segmented glomeruli

Access to EMBL Hamburg

- Proposal submission for 'single project', 'BAG', 1 deadline per annum
<https://smis.embl-hamburg.de>
- Rolling proposal - submission at any time
- **Supported transnational access**

- **Industrial access**

Biosaxs.com for SAXS
EMBLEM for SPC & MX

**EMBL Grenoble
MX / SAXS / Cryo-EM**

The EMBL-ESRF Joint Structural Biology Beamlines

ID23-1 (tunable)

EBSL8/ID29

ID30B (tunable)

**CM01 (Cryo-EM)
PSB operated**

ID23-2 (μ focus)

ID30-A3 (μ focus)

ID30-A1 (MASSIF)

BM29 (BioSAXS)

HTX Lab: Automated Protein to Structure pipelines

- Online Crystallography (protein to structure pipeline)
- Large scale Fragment and Ligand Screening
- Membrane proteins crystallization (LCP)
- **New** Plate-to-beam data collection (CrystalDirect at MASSIF1, cryogenic and RT)

High-throughput crystallization

CrystalDirect™ automated harvesting

Automated data collection

CRIMS Developed by EMBL Crystallization Information Management System

Automated data processing

e.g. GlobalPhasing Pipedream

Access to EMBL Grenoble

- **Access managed by ESRF**
 - Peer reviewed by ESRF review panel (BAG or rolling access)
 - <https://www.esrf.fr/UsersAndScience/UserGuide/Applying>

- **Supported transnational access**

- **Industrial access**

- ALPX s.a.s.
alpx-services.com

EMBL Heidelberg

Electron Microscopy

EMBL Imaging Centre

Open access
to new imaging technologies

Tailored project support
by expert technical staff

Advanced training
of users and facility staff

Commercialisation
of new technologies and workflows

Imaging across the scales of biology

EM and CLEM services

Sample vitrification

TEM data collection

Cellular tomography

Volume imaging

Instruments for EM and CLEM

Titan Krios G4

- Single particle analysis
- High-res tomography
- Cellular tomography

Glacios

- Sample screening
- Single particle analysis

Aquilos 2

- FIB-milling
- Lift out (coming soon)

Crossbeam 550

- FIB-milling
- volume imaging

LSM 900 Airyscan 2

- Cryo-Confocal LM

Tailored Project Support

Sample Preparation

Image Acquisition with High-Tech Instrumentation

Data Analysis

Access Modes

Direct Access

- Evaluated by the external referees of the project evaluation committee
- Users contribute to the maintenance costs of the microscopes and consumables of their experiments

Instruct - ERIC

- For researchers from Instruct member countries
- For all electron microscopy services & related techniques
- Costs related to microscope access, travel & accommodation can be funded

Euro-BioImaging – ERIC

- For researchers from Euro-BioImaging member countries
- For all light and correlative microscopy services & related techniques
- For some countries, costs related to microscope access, travel & accommodation can be funded

EC funded access schemes: iNEXT Discovery, Comulis, EOSC Life...

- For all researchers from Europe and beyond
- For electron microscopy services & related techniques, for cloud data services
- Costs related to microscope access, travel & accommodation can be funded

EMBL Imaging Centre

Cutting-edge electron and light microscopy technologies

ic-contact@embl.org

instruct-eric.eu

eurobioimaging.eu

inext-discovery.eu

eosc-life.eu

comulis.eu

Summary

- Many technologies for (4D) MX, SAXS, EM
 - ⇒ Portal webpage www.embl.org/services-facilities
- Funded access
 - ⇒ please get in touch.
- Integrated access
 - For non-specialists
 - For integrative structural biology
- Interest in working in experimental infrastructures?
 - PhD & postdoc positions
 - Instruct short-time fellowship
 - ARISE fellowships.

Instruct-ERIC member countries and organisations

Currently there are 14 countries and organisations who have signed up as members of the Instruct European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC). Each member pays an annual membership, which allows scientists from those countries to [submit their proposals](#) to gain access to the service/technologies catalogue, apply for [internships](#) and R&D [pilot project](#) funding, and access expert [training](#).

Member countries and organisations are shown in the table below. Click to view centre information, funding bodies and contact details for the country representatives.

Belgium	Latvia
Czech Republic	Lithuania
EMBL	Representative: Gintaras Valincius (Institute of Biochemistry, Vilnius University)
Finland	Netherlands
France	

Thank you!

Cryo-EM services: from sample to structure

Sample preparation for cryo-EM
by rapid plunge freezing

Sample screening to identify grids suitable
for high-end data collection

High-end data collection and data analysis

With John Atkins (University College of Cork) & Ahmad Jomaa (University of Virginia)

Fromm, *et al.* Nat Commun 2023